

Cyclic Voltammetric Studies on the Reduction of *p*-Nitroso-*N,N*-dialkylanilines in Cationic Surfactant

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Manuscript received 19 April 1993, revised 28 June 1993, accepted 17 September 1993

Electrochemical reduction of *p*-nitroso-*N,N*-dimethylaniline (PNDMA) and *p*-nitroso-*N,N*-diethylaniline (PNDEA) has been carried out using cyclic voltammetric technique in aqueous buffers of pH range 4–10. A two-electron reduction mechanism leading to the formation of hydroxylamine is proposed. Cationic micelle forming surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) inhibited the reduction process. Effect of CTAB on E_p , i_p , diffusion coefficient (D) and heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) has been discussed.

Electrochemical studies on some organic compounds in micellar media revealed that percent yield and product formation are dependent on the type of surfactant used¹. Surfactants have also been employed as selective masking agents and to improve sensitivity of the electrochemical analysis². Though electrochemical behaviour of nitroso compounds has been a subject of research³, reports on the electrochemical reduction of nitroso compounds in micellar media are a few⁴. As some antibiotics and carcinogenic compounds contain nitroso group⁵, studies on facile methods of reducing potentially toxic nitroso compounds to less harmful hydroxylamines assume importance. This prompted us to investigate the cyclic voltammetric reduction of *p*-nitroso-*N,N*-dimethylaniline (PNDMA) and *p*-nitroso-*N,N*-diethylaniline (PNDEA) in aqueous medium and in presence of micelle forming surfactant, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB).

Results and Discussion

Cyclic voltammetric scan of 1×10^{-4} M solution of PNDMA and PNDEA under HMDE showed only one cathodic peak in presence of all the supporting electrolytes chosen. This is attributed to the reduction of $-N=O$ group, the only electroactive site present in PNDMA

and PNDEA. A typical cyclic voltammogram in acetate buffer of pH 4 is shown in Fig. 1. Peak potential (E_p) is found to shift to negative side with increase in pH of the medium (Table 1). This indicates the involvement of protons in the rate-determining step. E_p is also

Fig. 1. Typical cyclic voltammogram of PNDMA in acetate buffer of pH 4; [Substrate] = 1×10^{-4} M, scan rate = 50 mV s^{-1} .

found to shift to more negative direction with increase in the concentration of nitroso compounds, suggesting that the reduction process is irreversible. This conclusion is also supported by the absence of anodic peak in the reverse scan of the cyclic voltammogram. Multicyclic voltammograms indicate that compounds get adsorbed on the

Fig. 2. Plots i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ for the reduction of PNDEA in (A) acetate buffer of pH 4, (B) phosphate buffer of pH 7 and (C) carbonate buffer of pH 10.

surface of the electrode during the reduction process. This conclusion is supported by the linear nature of i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ plots which does not pass through the origin (Fig. 2). Values

of transfer coefficient (αn_a), diffusion coefficient (D) and heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) for the reduction process have been calculated (Table 1). The order of diffusion coefficient is found to be same for both the compounds. The forward rate constant values are found to decrease with increase in pH, indicating that the reduction process becomes difficult as concentration of protons decreases.

Dependence of cyclic voltammetric parameters on CTAB concentration for the electrochemical reduction of substrates is investigated in all the supporting electrolytes chosen. Data in carbonate buffer of pH 10 for the reduction of PNDMA and PNDEA are given in Table 2. CTAB is found to inhibit the reduction process. The apparent diffusion coefficient values for the reduction of PNDMA and PNDEA decrease markedly with increase in surfactant concentration. This can be attributed to the adsorption of micellar aggregates on the electrode surface.

TABLE 1—TYPICAL CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF PNDMA AND PNDEA

[Substrate] = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$, scan rate = 50 mV s^{-1}

Parameter	In pH 4 Acetate buffer		In pH 7 Phosphate buffer		In pH 10 Carbonate buffer	
	PNDMA	PNDEA	PNDMA	PNDEA	PNDMA	PNDEA
E_p (V)	0.13	0.15	0.36	0.37	0.50	0.51
i_p (μA)	1.45	1.07	0.75	2.15	1.10	1.65
$D \times 10^5$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	6.30	3.46	1.68	13.80	3.60	8.15
$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm s^{-1})	2.14×10^{-6}	4.03×10^{-6}	1.58×10^{-10}	1.12×10^{-17}	1.38×10^{-16}	1.82×10^{-19}

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA ON CTAB CONCENTRATION IN CARBONATE BUFFER OF pH 10 FOR PNDMA and PNDEA

Scan rate = 50 mV s^{-1} , [Substrate] = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$

[CTAB] $\times 10^3 M$	E_p (V)		i_p (μA)		$D \times 10^5$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)		$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm s^{-1})	
	PNDMA	PNDEA	PNDMA	PNDEA	PNDMA	PNDEA	PNDMA	PNDEA
0	0.50	0.51	1.1	1.65	3.6	8.15	1.38×10^{-16}	1.82×10^{-19}
0.01	0.51	0.52	0.95	1.62	2.7	7.91	6.37×10^{-17}	1.64×10^{-23}
0.05	0.51	0.52	0.95	0.82	2.7	2.04	6.37×10^{-17}	3.7×10^{-17}
0.10	0.53	0.52	0.95	0.82	2.7	2.04	6.94×10^{-14}	3.7×10^{-17}
0.50	0.53	0.52	0.65	0.82	1.27	2.04	2.5×10^{-11}	3.7×10^{-17}
1.00	0.50	0.52	0.65	0.67	1.27	1.36	2.04×10^{-19}	3.7×10^{-17}
5.00	0.50	0.52	0.45	0.50	0.60	0.71	9.55×10^{-20}	2.7×10^{-17}
10.00	0.50	0.52	0.45	0.42	0.60	0.54	1.39×10^{-19}	1.5×10^{-11}
20.00	0.50	-	0.45	-	0.60	-	5.66×10^{-17}	-
40.00	0.50	-	0.35	-	0.36	-	4.6×10^{-17}	-
50.00	-	0.53	-	0.22	-	0.15	-	6.89×10^{-21}
60.00	0.49	-	0.35	-	0.36	-	4.99×10^{-15}	-
80.00	0.48	0.53	0.35	0.17	0.27	0.09	1.32×10^{-16}	2.32×10^{-23}

Decrease in the availability of electroactive sites due to solubilisation of the substrate by the micelles may also contribute to this effect. Observation of the data in Table 2 reveals that both i_p and D values sharply decrease at 5×10^{-4} M CTAB concentration for the reduction of PNDMA and 5×10^{-5} M CTAB concentration for the reduction of PNDEA. The results suggest that cationic micellar medium may be used for selective electrochemical reduction of mixture of nitroso compounds. Well-defined peaks are not observed in other supporting electrolytes in presence of CTAB. From the differential pulse polarograms recorded for the reduction of PNDMA and PNDEA, the half peak width ($\Delta W_{1/2}$) is obtained.

Using the equation⁶, $\Delta W_{1/2} = 90.4/n$, the number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process is found to be two. On the basis of the above results, the following mechanism is proposed for the electrochemical reduction of PNDMA and PNDEA.

Experimental

PNDMA and PNDEA were prepared and recrystallised following the reported methods⁷. AnalaR grade chemicals were used for the preparation of the supporting electrolytes. CTAB was used after recrystallising several times from acetone-alcohol mixture⁸. Acetate buffer of pH 4, phosphate buffer of pH 7 and carbonate buffer of pH 10 were used as supporting electrolytes. Cyclic

voltammograms and differential pulse polarograms were recorded on a PARC 264 A3 polarographic analyzer/stripping voltammeter equipped with PARC 303A static mercury drop electrode assembly and PARC RE 0150 X-Y recorder. The hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) of area 0.0096 cm² was used as working electrode and Ag/AgCl(s),Cl⁻ as reference electrode. All experiments were carried out at 298 ± 1 K.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (N.C.S. and K.M.R.) are grateful to the authorities of Regional Engineering College, Warangal, for providing financial assistance.

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